

C-IMMSIM simulation results

May 8, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. *Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer*. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.

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Allele: A0101
Pseudo sequence: KAVHAEQRNKAQTRA
Threshold: 9.456400
Max score: 29.236000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-044945_5_IVVC7ooJC27U.FSA_1_001

MRCIGIANRDFVEGVSGGSWVDIVLEHGSCVTTMAKNKPTLDFELIKTEAKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEP
SLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKIVQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGK
EVKITPQSSITEAELTYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVHRQWFLDPLPWLPGADTQGSNWIQKETLVTF
KNPHAKKQDVVVLGSGEGAMHTALTGATEIQMSSGNLLFTGHLKCLRMDKLQLKGMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTTI
VIRVQYEGDGPCKIPFEIMDLEKRHVLRGLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGDSYIIIGVPEPQLKLNWFKK

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 128 score=0.011000 unnormalised=1.2166000000 IVQPENLEY
1] pos= 169 score=0.041055 unnormalised=4.5406000000 ITEAELTYG
2] pos= -1 score=0.947945 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

=====
Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-044945_5_IVVC7ooJC27U.FSA_1_001

MRCIGIANRDFVEGVSGGSWVDIVLEHGSCVTTMAKNKPTLDFELIKTEAKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEP
SLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKIVQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGK
EVKITPQSSITEAELTYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVHRQWFLDPLPWLPGADTQGSNWIQKETLVTF
KNPHAKKQDVVVLGSGEGAMHTALTGATEIQMSSGNLLFTGHLKCLRMDKLQLKGMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTTI
VIRVQYEGDGPCKIPFEIMDLEKRHVLRGLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGDSYIIIGVPEPQLKLNWFKK

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 73 score=0.021013 unnormalised=2.2772000000 CPTQGEPSL
1] pos= 164 score=0.007781 unnormalised=0.8432000000 TPQSSITEA
2] pos= 241 score=0.003776 unnormalised=0.4092000000 NPHAKKQDV
3] pos= -1 score=0.967430 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

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SLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMKGKIVQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGK
EVKITPQSSITEAELTYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVHRQWFLDPLPWLPGADTQGSNWIQKETLVTF
KNPHAKKQDVVVLGSGEGAMHTALTGATEIQMSSGNLLFTGHLKCLRMDKLQLKGMSYSMCTGKFKVVKEIAETQHGTTI
VIRVQYEGDGPCKIPFEIMDLEKRHVLRGLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFPGDSYIIIGVPEPQLKLNWFKK

```

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0]      pos= 73 score=0.021013 unnormalised=2.2772000000      CPTQGEPSL
1]      pos= 164 score=0.007781 unnormalised=0.8432000000      TPQSSITEA
2]      pos= 241 score=0.003776 unnormalised=0.4092000000      NPHAKKQDV
3]      pos= -1 score=0.967430 unnormalised=104.8410000000      non-binding event

```

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DoPeptideList_II:
    Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
    NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

    Read class II peptide list from file? NO

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=====
Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

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```

-----
Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250508-044945_5_IVVC7ooJC27U.FSA_1_001
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MRCIGIANRDFVEGVSGGSWVDIVLEHGSCVTTMAKNKPTLDFELIKTEAKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEP
SLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMGKIVQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGK
EVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVHRQWFLDPLPWLPGADTQGSNWIQKETLVTF
KNPHAKKQDVVVLGSGQEGAMHTALTGATEIQMSSGNLLFTGHLKCRLRMDKLQLKGMSSYMCTGKFKVVKIEAETQHGTI
VIRVQYEGDGPCKIPFEIMDLEKRHVLRGLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFGDSYIIIGVEPGQLKLNWFKK

```

```

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0]      pos= 22 score=0.021941 unnormalised=1.9105600000      IVLEHGSCV
1]      pos= 136 score=0.015889 unnormalised=1.3835600000      YTIVITPHS
2]      pos= 180 score=0.033230 unnormalised=2.8935600000      VTMECSPRT
3]      pos= 192 score=0.021700 unnormalised=1.8895600000      FNEMVLLQM
4]      pos= 217 score=0.010974 unnormalised=0.9555600000      LPWLPGADT
5]      pos= 259 score=0.016693 unnormalised=1.4535600000      MHTALTGAT
6]      pos= 269 score=0.116893 unnormalised=10.1785600000      IQMSSGNLL
7]      pos= 350 score=0.002338 unnormalised=0.2035600000      LITVNPVIVT
8]      pos= 378 score=0.000454 unnormalised=0.0395600000      IIGVEPGQL
9]      pos= -1 score=0.759888 unnormalised=66.1680000000      non-binding event

```

```

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```

MRCIGIANRDFVEGVSGGSWVDIVLEHGSCVTTMAKNKPTLDFELIKTEAKQPATLRKYCIEAKLTNTTTDSRCPTQGEP
SLNEEQDKRFVCKHSMVDRGWNGCGLFGKGGIVTCAMFTCKKNMGKIVQPENLEYTIVITPHSGEEHAVGNNTGKHGK
EVKITPQSSITEAELTGYGTVTMECSPRTGLDFNEMVLLQMEDKAWLVHRQWFLDPLPWLPGADTQGSNWIQKETLVTF
KNPHAKKQDVVVLGSGQEGAMHTALTGATEIQMSSGNLLFTGHLKCRLRMDKLQLKGMSSYMCTGKFKVVKIEAETQHGTI
VIRVQYEGDGPCKIPFEIMDLEKRHVLRGLITVNPVIVTEKDRPVNIEAEPFGDSYIIIGVEPGQLKLNWFKK

```

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 22	score=0.021941	unnormalised=1.9105600000	IVLEHGSCV
1]	pos= 136	score=0.015889	unnormalised=1.3835600000	YTIVITPHS
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8]	pos= 378	score=0.000454	unnormalised=0.0395600000	IIGVEPGQL
9]	pos= -1	score=0.759888	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event
